

THE USER'S PERSPECTIVE ON MOBILE WALLET PAYMENT SYSTEM AND ITS DETERMINANTS

KAREN LICIA.D

MBA Student, Saveetha School of management, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences (SIMATS), Saveetha University, Chennai.

HANNAH WINCY.A

MBA Student, Saveetha School of management, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences (SIMATS), Saveetha University, Chennai.

Dr. P. PRAVEEN KUMAR

Associate Professor, Saveetha School of Management, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences (SIMATS), Saveetha University, Chennai. Email: praveenkumarp.ssm@saveetha.com

Abstract

Digital payments have brought unbelievable changes in the strategy of business and digital payment systems. The reason behind it is the increase of internet users. The business is now adopting the digital payment system strategy to gain competitive advantage. The digital wallet is very successful in developing countries especially like India. In India, the internet entry was well established because of the high usage of smart phone and as a result it created a great opportunity for bank to spread worldwide. Therefore, the mobile wallet company started to build on more features in the transaction payment system. This study is undertaken to analyse the mobile wallet payment system and its user satisfaction. For this survey, we used a quantitative survey method of a sample of 206 respondents. From this study it is found that most of the people prefer the mobile wallets for their regular transactions. It was also found that people find convenience and feel secure while using mobile wallets.

Keywords: M-Wallets, Innovation, Regulations, Satisfaction, Sustainable Development

INTRODUCTION

India's mobile wallet is prospering at high level because of the necessity of smart phone usage therefore it led to a drastic growth in usage of mobile wallet payment. Even the vendors nowadays use this transaction as it is convenient for the customer. The money wallet companies work on the business model of doing recharge, bill payments etc. In India they use open wallet, semi open wallet, closed wallet and semi closed wallet. The mobile wallet companies provide offers, discount to attract and gain customers. The digital wallet companies get brokerage of every sale for the service provided. Therefore, through its people get benefited more and more. Mobile Wallet is easy way for customers to make payments conveniently through mobile phones. With the help of mobile technology, the consumer can pay their bill, transfer the money, book tickets, online shopping anywhere at any time. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; David, Ahmed, Ganeshkumar & Sankar, 2020; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

Through mobile payment, customers save times, get user friendly applications and also feel secured. For this study, data have been collected from the users of Paytm, gpay, mobikwick, phonepe, free charge, jiomoney, ola money, airtel my app and paypal. This research is done to analyse the mobile wallet payment system and to know whether the customers are satisfied with the service provided by the mobile-wallet companies.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Amin et al. (2021) have examined the attitude of customer's upon mobile banking adoption and usage in Bangladesh. The users find mobile banking as an easy method for the cash transaction. The customers are very satisfied and have a positive attitude toward mobile banking.

Bhama & Priya (2020) have conducted a study on consumer perception towards usage of mobile wallets. Users found that mobile wallets as easy use and valuable method but the problem is with the network connection. From the study, it is concluded that Paytm is the mostly used mobile wallet among all the other wallets.

Ibrahim et al. (2020) have studied about the understanding of the youth perception and issues with a mobile wallet. In this study, it is found that majority of people are preferring followed by Paytm. People use mobile wallets about 5 times a week.

Subaramaniam et al. (2020) have studied that internet users are growing fast every day worldwide. This research shows the positive and negative influences of E-Wallets and M-wallets on users. The E-Wallet is rapidly increased due to E-Wallet or payment in this busy period. But many respondents prefer money in the hands because they think feel secures more than E-Wallet.

Joshi et al. (2019) have examined usage of Paytm practices on the users of urban India. The study was conducted for the street shopkeepers and small vendors by asking questions directly for analysing the usage of Paytm. The respondents concluded that usage of the Paytm wallet has raised their sales value.

Yuvaraj & Sheila Eveline (2018) have studied on consumer's perception on cashless transactions and information security in the digital economy users. In this study, it is found that consumer awareness plays a vital part in cashless transactions. Primary data has been collected with the help of the questionnaire method. SPSS software has been used for data analysis and chi-square test has been undertaken.

Punwatkar & Verghese (2018) examined the consumer's adaption behaviour towards the e-wallet payment system. The study was conducted to find the factors which affect the consumer's behaviour toward the adoption of e-wallets. It also measures the influence level of mobile wallets. This study concludes that the e-wallet payment system provides many benefits to the users. Taylor (2018) has studied the digital wallets and the role they play in the FinTech industry. They also found the factors that affect the mobile banking applications.

Adharsh (2018) studied that E-wallet payment seems to be a more consistent service to be used by smartphones. Most Indian young people are using mobile wallets. M-wallet users focus on

college-going students. The study reveals the factors that affect the youth in adopting M-wallets and the technique –adopted by organizations in keeping their customers consistently. Many of the used E-wallet services in India are Paytm, ICICI pocket, JioMoney, Airtel money, Citrus, etc. Young people mainly use E-wallets for digital transactions, ticket booking, top-ups, ease of usage and immediate transactions. Major factors for using E-wallet services are the availability of number of services.

Saxena, (2018) has conducted study to know about the role of mobile wallets in online shopping. Consumer awareness, consumer adoption status of mobile wallets, factors influencing the adoption of mobile wallets has been examined. For the data analysis, SPSS has been used. From the research, it is found that people prefer mobile wallets for shopping online

Babu (2018) has studied about awareness and preference towards digital payment mechanisms. In this study, the primary data was collected from 200 people using a questionnaire and Likert's 5-point scale. Study states that majority of people have good knowledge of the cashless payment system and they are using the digital payment system very often.

Desai (2018) has examined the preference of consumer's awareness about m-wallets and also finds which factors affect the decision making in Surat city. The researchers have prepared a structured questionnaire and have collected data. The findings revealed that awareness related to m-wallets is very high in Surat city. Age groups of 18-25 have the maximum knowledge about these services. Security and privacy are two key factors that have a direct effect on m-wallet. The study also finds that the many users preferred to use Paytm for their transaction.

Rana (2017) has done research on factors affecting the usage of mobile wallets, and demographic variables have been examined. It is concluded that people prefer mobile wallets for recharge, paying bills and transferring money.

Chauhan & Shingari (2017) have studied the future of E wallets. It is found that it was convenient to use cash back, fast service, instant availability, security, time consuming are the main factors in m-wallet service. It is concluded that the graduates are not fully satisfied with the service provider by the m-wallet companies.

Shankar & Kumari (2016) have studied the factors affecting the behavioural intentions towards mobile banking adoption in India. Factors include usefulness, awareness, and ease of use, self-efficiency, compatibility, security, privacy, risk, social influence and financial cost. This study concludes that out of all factors, usefulness is most important impactful factor whereas social influence has least impact.

MOBILE WALLET PAYMENT SYSTEM

The data for this study is collected from 206 respondents with 5-point Linkert scale questionnaire. The difference between the convenience/security factors of the m-wallet and the demographic profile of the respondents are discussed in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: Age Vs Convenience

S. No.	Convenience	F	Sig.
1	Saves time	.503	.734
2	Accessible 24/7	1.029	.394
3	Flexible procedures	.608	.657
4	User friendly	.430	.787
5	Makes easier purchase of product or service	.484	.748
6	Easier than other modes of payment	.331	.857

Since the sig. value is more than 0.05, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the age of respondents and their convenience in the usage of m-wallets. All the age category of people experiences the same level of comfort in the m-wallet.

Table 2: Gender Vs Security Factors

S. No.	Security Factors	T	Sig.
1	Highly reliable	-.788	.432
2	Provide trustworthy	- 1.335	.183
3	Ensure safety and security	-.738	.461
4	Error free transaction	-.728	.467
5	Safe from internet fraud	- 1.325	.187
6	Safe from theft of money	-.599	.550
7	Confidential bank details	- 1.350	.179
8	Provide accurate financial statement	-.953	.342

Since the sig. value is more than 0.05, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the gender of respondents and security factors pertaining to the m-wallet. The overall satisfaction of the users on the usage of the e-wallet and its determinants is discussed in Table 3.

Table 3: Overall Satisfaction and Its Determinants

S. No.	Variable / Factors	Mean* / Beta**	Sig. Value
1	Overall Satisfaction	4.21*	NA
2	Convenience Factors	1.43**	0.030
3	Security Factors	1.60**	0.010

Majority of the users are satisfied with the mobile wallet and the average mean value is 4.21. The significant value of convenience factors and security factors is less than 0.05. It is inferred that the user's satisfaction is highly influenced by the convenience and security factors pertaining to the m-wallet.

CONCLUSION

In recent times, India has developed a major digital platforms. After demonetization, most of the people updated themselves from real money transaction to digital transaction, though they

face difficulties in early stage of development later with the help of expansion of mobile wallet companies majority of the people got used to it because of convenience. The mobile wallet company made the best in implementing various features in their M-wallet but they lacked in security and safety. As many internet frauds are happening the people are losing hope towards the mobile wallet payment systems. Therefore the mobile wallet companies must make sure that they provide best safety and security measures and implement trust for the users.

REFERNACES

Amin, M. A., Sultana, N., Saha, T., Islam, S. N., & Kashem, M. A. (2021). Customer's Attitude toward Mobile Banking Usage: A Case Study in Bangladesh. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 0419–0426.

Babu, G. C. (2018). Awareness and Preference towards digital payment mechanism-A study of customer perceptions. *International Research Journal of management science and technology*, 9 (3), 352-361.

Benita, M. S. (2021). Are the student migrants satisfied with life? Effect of acculturative stress and perceived discrimination. *International Journal of Education Economics and Development*, 12(1), 79-96.

Bhama, K. K., & Priya, C. S. (2020). A Study on Consumer Perception towards Usage of Mobile Wallets

Chauhan, M., & Shingari, I. (2017). Future of e-Wallets: A Perspective From Under Graduates'. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, 7(8), 146. <https://doi.org/10.23956/ijarcsse.v7i8.42>

Chauhan, M., & Shingari, I. (2017). Future of e-Wallets: A Perspective from Under Graduates'. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, 7(8), 146. <https://doi.org/10.23956/ijarcsse.v7i8.42>

David, A., Ahmed, R. R., Ganeshkumar, C., & Sankar, J. G. (2020). Consumer Purchasing Process of Organic Food Product: An Empirical Analysis. *Calitatea*, 21(177), 128-132.

Desai, M. P. (2018). A study on preference of consumers towards m-wallet in Surat city. *Journal of Modern Management & Entrepreneurship (JMME)*, 08, 6-10.

Ibrahim, M., Kaur, H., & Munjal, G. (2020). Youth's Perception towards Mobile Wallets: Issues and Challenges. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(16).

Kumar, P. P. (2020). Effectiveness of Marketing Strategy Formulation in Biomedical Healthcare Industry.

Kumar, P. P., & Shree, K. C. (2018). Determinants of Vendor-Client Relationship in Medical Equipment Industry. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*, 9(10).

Kumar, P. P., & Shree, K. C. (2019). Green human resource management: An access device to evade exhaustion of natural resources. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 8(11), 740–743.

Monica, B. (2021). The Effect of IT Employees' Engagement on Work Attitudes through Cloud Computing Services. In *Recent Advances in Technology Acceptance Models and Theories* (pp. 497-507). Springer, Cham.

Monica, B. S., & Supriya, M. V. (2019). Acculturative stress of internal migrants: impact on work attitudes. *International Journal of Human Resources Development and Management*, 19(2), 150-165.

Punwatkar, S., & Verghese, (2018). Adaptation of e-Wallet Payment: An Empirical Study on Consumers' Adoption Behavior in Central India. *International Journal of Advanced in Management, Technology and Engineering Sciences*, 1147-1156.

R. Adharsh, J. Harikrishnan, Adarsh Prasad & J.S. Venugopal (2018), Transformation towards E-Wallet Payment Systems Pertaining to Indian Youth, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 119 (12),

2583-2594

Rana, S. S. (2017). A study on preference towards the mobile wallets among the university students in Lucknow City. *Scholedge International Journal of Management and development*, 4 (6), 46-57

Saxena, N. (2017). Role of Mobile wallets in Online Shopping. 106–116.

Shankar, A., & Kumari, P. (2016). Factors affecting mobile banking adoption behavior in India. *The Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*, 21(1).

Subaramaniam, K., Kolandaisamy, R., Jalil, A. B., & Kolandaisamy, I. (2020). The Impact of E-Wallet for Current Generation. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*

Taylor, T. (2018). Rise of Digital Wallet and What They Mean For The Fintech Industry. *Techgenix*.

V. J, Mahesh & Uma Rani, P. (2019). Impact of Promotional Strategies on Viewers of Kollywood Movies. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 8(10), pp. 1140–1144

V. J, Mahesh, Gigi, G.S., & Uma Rani, P. (2019). Movie promotional strategies in Tamil film industry-the contemporary access. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 8(11), pp. 712–717

William Robert P, R. Monisha (2019) .A Research on Factors of Forex Procedures in Private Bank. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 8(11s), 777- 781.Scopus Indexed-e-ISSN: 2278-3075.

Yuvaraj, S., & Sheila Eveline, N. (2018). Consumers' perception towards cashless transactions and information security in the digital economy. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology*, 9(7), 89–9